

**Delivering the next generation of open
Integrated Assessment MOdels for
Net-zero, sustainable Development**

D6.2 – Open data management plan – Update 1

WP6 – Open

31/05/2024

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the European Union

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This report can be used internally by all consortium partners to guide all data management activities of the project. It can be also used by researchers outside the DIAMOND consortium as an example for informing their own data management strategy (especially for other Horizon Europe projects).

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The current report documents the second version of the open Data Management Plan (DMP) of DIAMOND. As in the initial DMP report (D6.1), this report includes a description of the data that will be used and generated during the project; a strategy and an allocation of resources and responsibilities for achieving Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data; and details on how we shall ensure data security and correct handling of all ethical aspects. While this updated report does not introduce any changes or additions to the data practices that have been established in the original DMP, it additionally includes a section documenting all project datasets, journal articles, and deliverables that have been published as of May 2024. All such publications and datasets are provided as open access on the DIAMOND project's website and Zenodo community, and—in the case of journal articles—on the websites of their publishers. Again, in parallel with this report, we have developed and maintain a machine-actionable data management plan¹ (maDMP) using the ARGOS service of OpenAIRE. This maDMP is continuously updated with metadata for all datasets generated from project activities. The DMP report will be updated once more in Month 36 of the project (November 2025).

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report and the DIAMOND maDMP hosted in ARGOS.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781424>

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA'COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY SYSTEM OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

This report is an update to the initial version of the open Data Management Plan (DMP) of DIAMOND, which was published in March 2023 (Month 4). In general, all versions of the DMP include the following information:

1. a description of the types and formats of data that are and will be generated and collected during the project, including the origin, size, and utility of the data;
2. a brief description of the project models that (will) process this data;
3. a strategy and an allocation of resources and responsibilities for achieving Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data;
4. details on how we (will) ensure data security and correct handling of all ethical aspects.

The current update does not include any changes or additions to the data practices established in the initial DMP. Nevertheless, it provides an exhaustive documentation of all datasets, articles, and deliverables that have been published acknowledging DIAMOND (and associated funding). Overall, five datasets and seven project deliverables have been released, as of May 2024, and are provided as open access on the DIAMOND project's website and Zenodo community. In addition, eleven journal articles acknowledging DIAMOND have been published (as fully open access). The articles are thus freely available on the websites of their publishers and are also referenced within the dedicated section of the DIAMOND website with the aim to increase their findability.

In parallel with this report, a machine-actionable data management plan² (maDMP) has been developed for DIAMOND using the ARGOS service of OpenAIRE. The maDMP has been and will be continuously updated with metadata for all datasets generated from project activities. The DMP report will be updated once more in Month 36 of the project (November 2025).

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781424>

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List of Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
maDMP	machine-actionable Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology
CC	Creative Commons
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

1 Introduction

This report is the second version of the open Data Management Plan (DMP) of the Horizon Europe DIAMOND project. The DMP outlines guidelines and procedures on the collection, generation, processing, and sharing of data throughout the duration of the project. The report mainly includes information on the expected data, including a description of model data inputs/outputs, data formats, data sources, as well as practices for data processing, curation, and preservation (Chapter 2). The report will cover the whole lifecycle of project data, including data handling during and after the project, along with a detailed strategy to ensure that this data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR; see Chapter 3). It will also delineate DIAMOND's Open Science strategy, i.e., how we will ensure that all data and project outputs will be open access and that all project-developed applications and models will be open source, along with the required allocation of project resources to accomplish this strategy (Chapter 4). Apart from data accessibility, the report will discuss security (Chapter 5) and ethical aspects (Chapter 6) related to data collection and use.

In parallel with this document, a machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP) was developed using the ARGOS service of the OpenAIRE³ (Figure 1). The maDMP is an online collection of rich metadata for all datasets that have been and will be developed during the project as well as specific guidelines for each dataset, for instance, on how the dataset will be shared and whether it is linked to another project output, e.g., publications. The datasets themselves will be stored in Zenodo⁴ which is a digital repository that follows the desired principles of Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology (TRUST principles; see Lin et al., 2020), while the maDMP will provide links to them. Through the ARGOS service, the maDMP can be read by both humans and machines and connect to OpenAIRE and European Open Science Cloud⁵, improving the reusability and findability potential of the data. The maDMP is a "living document", to be updated immediately upon publication of a project dataset in Zenodo, without having to wait for the periodic updates of the DMP report (in this case, the final update in November 2025). Nevertheless, DMP reports will also provide summaries of all datasets that are currently present in the maDMP, as illustrated in Chapter 8 of the current report. Chapter 7 of this report provides a strategy on how new datasets will be added in the maDMP as well as on the roles of the different consortium partners in this process. Based on the experience of the partners with this strategy, adaptations will be made as needed.

³ <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/publicOverview/de2a89ba-9d7a-48ab-ab64-ecab2bd19674>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/diamond/>

⁵ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu>

Figure 1. A screenshot of the Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan of DIAMOND in ARGOS

As most model development tasks of the project are still ongoing, while scenario modelling activities have not yet practically started, there has been no need to adapt the data management practices introduced in the first DMP. Nevertheless, an extra chapter has been added (Chapter 8), listing all deliverables that have been produced in the context of the project as well as journal publications and accompanying datasets that have been acknowledging DIAMOND. Overall, 11 journal articles, five datasets, and seven deliverables have been published as of May 2024. The report DMP will be further updated in Month 36, documenting any potential changes to the project's data practices as well as enriching the list of publications and datasets.

2 Data Description

2.1 Project objectives and implications for data collection and generation

The main objective of DIAMOND is to comprehensively upgrade six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that have been instrumental in underpinning policy and research related to climate change mitigation. Apart from enhancing their existing capabilities, e.g., increasing their sectoral and technological detail as well as their spatial and temporal resolution, we will also develop new features allowing the models to widen the scope of the research questions they can address, including trade-offs of climate transitions with circular economy, adaptation efforts, and more. Additionally, by informing model development with insights and methods from psychology, behavioural economics, finance and economics research, and other fields, we will enable the models to explore interactions among climate pathways, political feasibility, societal desirability, distributional concerns, and more pertinent issues. All new models will be completely open source and their development will be informed by relevant communities of practice and stakeholder interactions. Then, using these advanced new models, DIAMOND aims to evaluate diverse scenarios on how to achieve climate neutrality at a global, European, and national scale as well as contribute to relevant scientific and policy assessments.

Based on these objectives, the data collection and generation of the project will revolve around the development and use of the six new models. First, we will need to ensure that all new model code will be open source and that interested parties outside the consortium have access to and a say on model development. For this, we will use best practices and paradigms from open-source software development, ensure that all new model code is uploaded on GitHub⁶ or other open code repositories (e.g., GitLab⁷ or Bitbucket⁸), and engage relevant communities of practice by participating or organising relevant events. Second, we will need to compile the data that will be used as an input for the models, which will be based on datasets and insights from the various disciplines involved in the project, ideally from open access sources. In the case of multi-model assessments that will be run during the project, we will also need to assess the harmonisation of input data among the various models. Third, based on the priorities and needs of project stakeholders, we will develop scenarios that will be run by the models. This will create a plethora of new modelling results, which will be then communicated to all interested parties through scientific publications, policy briefs, and business guides.

Apart from these three potential outlets, all input data of DIAMOND models, outputs of scenario analysis, and links to modelling code in GitHub will be hosted in the data sharing platform I²AM PARIS⁹. The platform was developed by project coordinator ICCS and project partners Holistic and BC3 in the context of the H2020 PARIS REINFORCE project, with the aim to establish a portal for the modelling community in support of climate policy and research. Currently, the platform allows modelling teams to host detailed documentation for their models and to develop interactive visualisations to describe the results of modelling exercises. Apart from storing new modelling documentation and scenario results, DIAMOND aims to go one step further and produce applications for different stakeholders based on these results. In that way, the project aims to bridge the gap between simply disseminating modelling results to stakeholders and ensuring that these results become directly exploitable for different audiences, such as policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and the civil society.

⁶ <https://github.com>

⁷ <https://about.gitlab.com>

⁸ <https://bitbucket.org>

⁹ <https://i2am-paris.eu>

2.2 Types and formats of data to be generated and collected

Each of the project activities described in Section 2.1 will require and generate different kinds of data. Table 1 shows a non-exhaustive list of the data types and formats that will be used per project activity. Data used for modelling inputs will be mostly quantitative and based on datasets in spreadsheet format (e.g., xlsx or csv) or prebuilt data (e.g., Rda format used for the R language). Turning to modelling development, new model code will be in the format of the programming languages used to develop these models. For instance, GCAM development will be mostly based on the C++ and R languages and, thus, its code will be documented in their respective file formats. Qualitative insights from previous reports and publications and from stakeholder co-creation activities will be also used to inform modelling. As with most data inputs, the outputs of the scenario analysis performed in DIAMOND will be also quantitative and exported in a spreadsheet format or other formats that are easily converted to spreadsheets. These output datasets will inform the scientific and policy publications of the project which will be provided in pdf formats.

Table 1. Data types and formats per project activity

Project activity	Data collected and generated	Data formats
Develop the new models	Collect: Code from previous versions of models, feedback from project stakeholders and communities of practice for the different models	File formats related to the programming language of each model (e.g., py, R, h, cpp, GAMS), reports documenting stakeholder feedback in pdf
	Generate: New model code	
Compile the input data for the new models	Collect: National and sectoral statistics on socioeconomics, energy use and supply, industrial indicators, finance, etc.; policy options; technological innovation data; costs; behavioural and consumption patterns of citizens; material use and consumption; data on land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF); and other modelling inputs	xlsx, csv, txt, json
	Generate: Curate the raw data into a format and data structure that is usable by project models	
Scenario analysis using the new models	Collect: Scenario definitions based on the stakeholder engagement activities of the project	Reports documenting stakeholder feedback in pdf
	Generate: GHG emissions, jobs created, costs and other social, economic, and environmental indicators	xlsx, csv, txt, json

2.2.1 Data processing tools

Models will be the main data processing tools used in the project. Table 2 shows all new models that are being

developed in DIAMOND, along with the existing models that the new ones are based on, their scope, and the partners that develop them. With the exception of OMNIA, all new models will eventually have a different scope from their base models, e.g., GCAM-Europe will provide a detailed modelling of the European area that will be based on the original global GCAM model. Based on their data inputs, the new models will process the scenarios and narratives suggested by DIAMOND stakeholders to quantitative results for a variety of indicators and for multiple years in the future (at least to 2050 and, for some models, until 2100). See Section 2.2.2 for more examples of data inputs and outputs. All new models will be open source and will be shared in GitHub or other open-source repositories. In addition, in the context of activities of Work Package (WP) 6 of the project, we will publish all models along with their requirements as Docker images, allowing external users to run the models without the need of installing anything. Similarly, we will publish snippets for post-processing analysis and visualisation through online Jupyter Notebooks in Binder.

Table 2. Models developed by the DIAMOND project

New models	Base models	Scope of new models	Responsible partner(s)
GCAM-Europe	GCAM ¹⁰	Europe	BC3, UMD, ICCS
OMNIA	TIMES-GEO ¹¹	Global	Imperial, UCL, E4SMA, ESMIA
CLEWs-EU	GLUCOSE, CLEWs ¹² , OSeMOSYS ¹³	Europe	Imperial, Cyl, ICCS
GEMINI-E3 EU	GEMINI-E3 ¹⁴	Europe	EPFL
NEMESIS-World	NEMESIS ¹⁵	Global	SEURECO
OPEN-PROM	PROMETHEUS ¹⁶	Global	E3M

We will also use specialised models that will be linked with all or with a subset of the six main IAMs (see Table 3), including the ENGAGE model for circular economy modelling, MAgPIE for land-use modelling, SILICONE and OpenSCM for modelling of climate impacts and non-CO₂ GHG-emissions, CHANCE and FIDELIO for household heterogeneity, and OpenTEPES for detailed electricity modelling. The auxiliary models will be pre-configured with their own data inputs, and they are going to be soft linked to the IAMs in order to provide the additional functionalities. We will also ensure that all input data for these models is open access, and their code is open source.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/JGCRI/gcam-core>

¹¹ https://www.i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc/times-geo

¹² https://www.i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc/clews

¹³ https://www.i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc/osemosys

¹⁴ https://www.i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc/gemini_e3

¹⁵ https://www.i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc/nemesis

¹⁶ <https://e3modelling.com/modelling-tools/prometheus/>

Table 3. Auxiliary models that will be linked to the new DIAMOND models

Auxiliary models	Functionality	Responsible partner(s)
ENGAGE ¹⁷	Circular economy modelling	UCL
MAgPIE ¹⁸	Land-use modelling	Imperial, Oxford
SILICONE ¹⁹ , OpenSCM	Climate modelling	CICERO
CHANCE ²⁰ , FIDELIO	Household heterogeneity	BC3, CESAR
OpenTEPES ²¹	Electricity modelling	IIT

Apart from models, other data processing tools that will be used are Microsoft Excel for reading and modifying xlsx and csv files, Microsoft Word for writing reports and manuscripts based on project results, and Adobe Reader/Acrobat for producing and reading publications in pdf format. It is also envisioned that other tools and scripting languages will be used for data processing and curating, such as Python and R.

2.2.2 Data inputs and outputs for models

Since the new IAMs will be developed during the project, it is still unclear what will be the final set of data that will be used in the new models. While some of the data from the base models will be re-used in the new ones, new variables might also be needed, or existing variables need to be substituted with alternative ones to adhere to the open-access strategy of the project. Similarly, auxiliary models are not yet configured to fully understand their needs in data inputs and the exact data outputs they produce. Table 4 shows an indicative list of data inputs and outputs for these models, based on a similar list developed for the DMP of the PARIS REINFORCE project²². Since many models that participated in PARIS REINFORCE will also serve as base models of DIAMOND (e.g., GCAM, TIMES-GEO, GEMINI-E3, NEMESIS), many data inputs and outputs shown in Table 4 are expected to be present in the new models too. The list will be expanded and finalised in the next and final update of the DIAMOND DMP.

Table 4. Indicative input and output data for project models

Data type	Category	Input/output
Population	Socioeconomic	Input
GDP	Socioeconomic	Input & output
Employment	Socioeconomic	Input & output

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10368-017-0385-3>

¹⁸ <https://rse.pik-potsdam.de/doc/magpie/4.2.1/>

¹⁹ <https://silicone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁰ https://www.i2am-paris.eu/detailed_model_doc/chance

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2022.101070>

²² https://paris-reinforce.eu/sites/default/files/2022-12/D8.8%20Data%20Management%20Plan-Update%202022_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

Data type	Category	Input/output
Total gross/real disposable income	Socioeconomic	Input & output
Interest rates and exchange rates	Socioeconomic	Input
Labour participation and productivity	Socioeconomic	Input
Household size and space	Socioeconomic	Input
Physical activity data	Socioeconomic	Input
Macroeconomic and sectoral activity data	Socioeconomic	Input & output
GHG emissions (CO ₂ , methane, others)	Emissions	Input & output
CO ₂ emission factors	Emissions	Input
Abatement curves	Emissions	Input
Water availability	Impacts	Input
Water withdrawal/consumption	Impacts	Output
Air quality (e.g., PM2.5)	Impacts	Output
Installed capacity for different energy technologies and for storage	Energy	Input & output
Electricity and heat production mix	Energy	Input & output
Specifications of energy technologies and availability	Energy	Input
Potential of renewable energy sources	Energy	Input
Network infrastructure specifications	Energy	Input
Conversion technology characteristics	Energy	Input
Sectoral energy intensities	Energy	Input & output
Energy/electricity trade	Energy	Input & output
Food/agricultural demand	AFOLU	Input & output
Land uses, types, and potential as emissions sinks	AFOLU	Input
Energy performance of buildings (HVAC, envelope, appliances)	Buildings	Input
Energy efficiency improvements rates	Buildings/Industry	Input

Data type	Category	Input/output
Industrial technologies - specifications and availability	Industry	Input
Sectoral productivity and growth	Industry	Input & output
Vehicle fleet and structure	Transport	Input & output
Technological characteristics of vehicles	Transport	Input
Fuel efficiency	Transport	Input
Mobility characteristics and modal shifts	Transport	Input & output
Energy prices	Prices/costs	Input & output
Energy and power technology costs	Prices/costs	Input & output
Cost of technologies (all sectors)	Prices/costs	Input

Notes: Data adapted from the DMP of PARIS REINFORCE.

2.2.3 Data used in scenario analysis

Apart from the data inputs shown in the previous section, DIAMOND models will need inputs related to specific scenarios to explore. Most of these inputs will be produced during the engagement and outreach activities of the project and will relate to pertinent policy and research questions that stakeholders want to explore with the new models. An indicative list of policies to explore is adapted by the DMP of the PARIS REINFORCE project and shown in Table 5. Other inputs for explorative scenario modelling will be based on assumptions on the variables mentioned in Table 4, such as whether some technologies are available or not and various assumptions on their costs and other characteristics (e.g., energy conversion efficiencies). More details on potential scenario inputs are provided in the Model Development Strategy of the DIAMOND project (see Deliverable 3.1 in the project website²³).

Table 5. Indicative policies that can be explored in project scenarios

Policy	Type of measures
Targets for emissions or global temperature	Targets
Climate change adaptation measures	Targets
Targets on efficiency performance	Targets
Targets on the energy mix	Targets

²³ <https://climate-diamond.eu/publications/deliverables/>

Policy	Type of measures
Targets for afforestation and protected lands	Targets
Carbon pricing	Economic
Carbon sink pricing	Economic
Land use change emissions tax	Economic
Energy taxes	Economic
Carbon border adjustments	Economic
COVID-19 recovery efforts	Economic
Regulations on emissions, energy, efficiency	Regulations
New standards on buildings, fuels, etc.	Regulations
Promotion of behavioural change	Social
International collaboration schemes (e.g., climate clubs)	Foreign policy
Changes in global supply chains (e.g., Europe's current efforts to reduce its reliance on Russian natural gas)	Foreign policy

Notes: Some policies were adapted from the DMP of PARIS REINFORCE.

2.3 Origin of the data and re-use of existing data

As discussed in the previous sections, the development of the new models will be based on the existing code and structure of their base models while their inputs will be based on existing data sources. These inputs will be enhanced significantly with the insights and datasets from the various disciplines participating in DIAMOND, including from psychology, finance, and industrial ecology, and will be based on an extensive review of the relevant literature (both peer-reviewed and grey) and available datasets. In addition, a significant goal of the project would be to find ways to open-up both modelling code and input data. This indicates that all existing model code that cannot be opened needs to be adapted or circumvented to allow new models to be fully open source, while all data inputs will need to be open access. The latter is one of the most challenging aspects of the Open Science strategy of the project since many significant data sources for modelling are proprietary or not publicly available, such as the results from some of the analyses of IEA. Strategies to achieve fully open-access data inputs will be drawn out during the project in a case-by-case basis and will aim to substitute proprietary datasets with similar open-source data. In case this is not possible, another potential solution will be to convert input data in a prebuilt, binary format which can be only read by the models and can be potentially shared openly. For instance, the GCAM model uses such binary datasets for reading data from IEA balances. An indicative list of data inputs used in the existing models that are publicly available and can be directly used by the new models is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Open-access data from the base models that can be re-used by the new models

Data sources	Use	Base models using the data
EUROSTAT	Energy balance sheets, energy prices, macroeconomic and sectoral activity data, population data and projection, physical activity data, CO ₂ emission factors and EU ETS registry for allocating emissions between ETS and non ETS	NEMESIS
EU reference scenarios	Potential calibration of NEMESIS to nuclear and hydro share in electricity mix and exogeneous energy efficiency	NEMESIS
EPA abatement curves	Calibration	GCAM, PROMETHEUS
IPCC Shared Socioeconomic Pathways	Population qualification projections	GCAM, PROMETHEUS, NEMESIS, TIMES-GEO
FAOSTAT balances	Food demand, agriculture	GCAM
UN	World Population projections	PROMETHEUS, GEMINI-E3
UNSD	Energy balances	TIMES-GEO
ClimateWatchData	GHG emissions	PROMETHEUS
OECD	GEMINI-E3: data for calibration of indirect taxation and government expenditures; NEMESIS: data for calibration of long-term project of GDP in non-EU countries (complementary to Eurostat)	NEMESIS, GEMINI-E3
IMF	GEMINI-E3: data for calibration of indirect taxation and government expenditures; NEMESIS: data for short/medium-term GDP projections for non-EU countries	NEMESIS, GEMINI-E3,
CEPII	alternative to OECD long-term GDP projections for non-EU countries	NEMESIS
World Input-Output Database	To complete EUROSTAT on imports and exports	NEMESIS
OECD/ITF	Transportation data	TIMES-GEO
Global Energy Assessment	Energy end-use in transport and buildings	TIMES-GEO

Notes: The list is adapted from the DMP of PARIS REINFORCE.

Apart from re-used data, a large volume of new data will be produced based on the co-creation activities of the project, as stakeholders' feedback will guide both the new model development and scenario analysis of DIAMOND. During the project, stakeholders will be able to provide their perspectives on what is currently missing from the wide IAM ecosystem and what features are required for new models. Communities of practice will be also invited to participate in and inform the development of the new models, including communities behind the creation and maintenance of the existing models such as the GCAM, IEA-ETSAP, and OSeMOSYS/CLEWs communities as well as wider modelling communities such as the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC). These practitioners and researchers, along with policymakers and representatives from the industry and civil society, will also help define the scenarios that will be modelled during the project. These stakeholder perspectives will be recorded and stored appropriately, based on GDPR guidelines (see Chapter 5) and adequate ethical treatment (see Chapter 6).

2.4 Expected size of the data

Based on previous modelling-based projects such as PARIS REINFORCE²⁴, the total size of data that is expected to be collected, processed, and produced will be around 250GB. Most of this size is expected to result from the data inputs that will be used in the new models, and, especially, from the sheer amounts of data outputs that will be produced. Other types of data that can be relatively heavy include the audio and video recordings of consortium and stakeholder meetings, which should be at a scale of hundreds of MB for each meeting, multiplied by a few dozens of meetings that will be organised. On the other hand, the minutes of these meetings will be documented in a small number of reports which will not be more than a few MB each. Model publications are also expected to not take too much space, considering that they will be around 60-80 pdf documents. More accurate estimations will be available during the project and the next revision of the DMP.

2.5 Data utility

The data outputs that will be produced by DIAMOND are expected to be useful to all expected audiences of the project. The new models will be directly useful to climate-economy modellers and other researchers while they will be also indirectly useful to policymakers, industry, and civil society representatives. The results of the scenario analysis will be useful to the same target audiences and inform their policies, strategies, research, and other activities. We will especially focus our efforts to disseminate project data to the European Commission and EU agencies, national/local governments, businesses, energy-intensive industries, financial institutions, and researchers of the broader climate modelling landscape (mitigation, impacts, adaptation).

²⁴ https://paris-reinforce.eu/sites/default/files/2022-12/D8.8%20Data%20Management%20Plan-Update%202022_v1.00_SUBMITTED.pdf

3 FAIR Data Guidelines

3.1 Making Data Findable

We will ensure that all project outputs are findable by using adequate identifiers and metadata. All deliverables and policy briefs will be uploaded in a Zenodo community that has been specifically created for the project²⁵ and where they will be automatically fitted with persistent digital object identifiers (DOIs). In the case of scientific publications, a DOI will be provided by the publishing journal, although we will still upload publications (or accepted manuscripts) in Zenodo and, potentially, also preprints. A versioning system will be also employed to track the state of each publication and ensure that interested parties can find the version they are looking for. For this, we will use Zenodo's paradigm where each new version gets a separate DOI, but a top-level DOI is also available, resolving to the latest version available. When each document is uploaded in Zenodo or on a journal, we will add adequate keywords to facilitate document retrieval via search engines. We will also use a consistent naming system for each type of publication:

- Scientific publications: "author(s)_name(s)_year" (e.g., Smith_et_al_2023.pdf)
- Policy briefs: "DIAMOND_Policy_Brief_Title" (e.g., DIAMOND_Policy_Brief_IAMs_In_Policy.pdf)
- Deliverable: "DIAMOND_DXX_Title" (e.g., DIAMOND_D6.2_Open_Data_Management_Plan_Update_1.pdf)

Datasets of project outputs that underpin publications will also be archived in Zenodo and fitted with a DOI and adequate keywords. We will then link all datasets in Zenodo with the maDMP in ARGOS²⁶ and accompany them with rich metadata, using the Horizon Europe template provided in ARGOS (see Chapter 7 for more information). Similarly, all model code will be stored in public repositories in GitHub which will be then linked to Zenodo and the maDMP.

All model code, documentation, inputs, and outputs will be also published in the I²AM PARIS modelling platform which will be continuously promoted as an integrated hub of information for the climate-economy and energy modelling community. For each dataset, we will include links to all related project publications in Zenodo and scientific journals to further increase findability. Finally, both the platform and the project website will include enough relevant content and an optimised sitemap structure to ensure findability in search engines like Google and Bing.

3.2 Making Data Openly Accessible

All project deliverables, policy briefs, and datasets will be published in Zenodo under Creative Commons licenses. In most cases, we will publish project outputs using the highly permissive CC BY license (version 4.0). Exceptionally, we may also consider less permissive licenses such as CC BY-NC to restrict commercial uses of project outcome, but only when this is necessary for specific and clear reasons by the author(s) of the publication or the dataset.

Similarly, scientific publications of the project will be published in journals offering open-access options in compliance with the Horizon Europe rules. When possible, we will publish in fully open-access journals, also considering the Open Research Europe publishing platform. In case that the available fully open-access options do not align with the scope of a publication, we will select a journal that offers a gold open-access option from

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/diamond/>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781424>

the list of journals that the organisations of project partners have a publishing agreement with. In that way, we will ensure that all project insights become immediately available and exploitable by project audiences. In case that a project deliverable is linked to a scientific publication, we will still add the deliverable in Zenodo, but we may add an appropriate embargo period so that the deliverable becomes publicly available only after the paper is published.

All new models developed by the project will be published under open-source licenses. In some cases, such as GCAM-Europe, we will use the same license as the one for the base model. Table 7 shows the licenses that have been tentatively selected for the new models. It is noted that these licenses refer to the model code and not the input data. In the case of input data, there are still some pending issues with the use of publicly restricted datasets in some of the base models and for which we are exploring open-access alternatives. The selection of licences for both model code and input data will be finalised later in the project.

Table 7. Selection of open-source licenses to use for new model code

New models	Open-source licence
GCAM-Europe	Educational Community License v2.0 ²⁷ (same as base model, GCAM)
OMNIA	MIT ²⁸
CLEWs-EU	Apache License 2.0 ²⁹ (same as base model, OSeMOSYS)
GEMINI-E3 EU	Undecided yet
NEMESIS-World	MIT
OPEN-PROM	GNU AGPLv3 ³⁰ , adding the “Commons Clause” to restrict commercial use ³¹

In terms of file formats, we will strive to use well-known formats that can be opened by freeware software such as pdf, csv, txt, mp3, and mp4 files. We will strive to avoid sharing content through proprietary file formats such as docx and xlsx. When this is not feasible (for instance, when we need to publish spreadsheet files with multiple tabs), we will accompany files in proprietary formats with links to compatible freeware software such as the Open Office suite.

We will also ensure that all open project outputs will remain available for as long as possible. All project publications and datasets will be published in established online repositories such as Zenodo and GitHub where high availability is expected for many years to come. This is especially the case for Zenodo where its operation is supported by the EU. The project website will be also kept online for at least three years after the project’s end to support the dissemination and findability of project outcomes. Project coordinator ICCS and project partner HOLISTIC will also ensure the longevity of the I²AM PARIS platform for at least three years after DIAMOND’s end (till around 2030). The partners will also undertake efforts to ensure the platform’s sustainability, either by future projects that will take over its operation or through appropriate funding mechanisms. The Horizon Results Booster

²⁷ <https://choosealicense.com/licenses/ecl-2.0/>

²⁸ <https://choosealicense.com/licenses/mit/>

²⁹ <https://choosealicense.com/licenses/apache-2.0/>

³⁰ <https://choosealicense.com/licenses/agpl-3.0/>

³¹ <https://commonsclause.com/>

service of the EU will be also consulted to find these mechanisms.

3.3 Making Data Interoperable

We will achieve high interoperability of project data by using adequate data formats and by providing informative metadata. As suggested in Section 3.2, all project datasets and reports of the project will be shared through widespread formats such as pdf, csv, and txt, avoiding proprietary formats when possible. The documentation of all new models along with the results of the scenario analysis will be formatted based on the IPCC AR6 reporting templates, ensuring that the wider climate-economy modelling community can use them, while also achieving interoperability with other relevant platforms of the community such as the Scenario Explorers by IIASA. Metadata for all project datasets will be added in DIAMOND's maDMP in ARGOS, using the format template of Horizon Europe. As the maDMP is machine actionable, it will be fairly easy to read the internal representation of metadata and potentially convert it to another format, further ensuring the interoperability of project datasets.

3.4 Making Data Reusable

As suggested in the previous section on open access, by releasing all deliverables and datasets through CC BY license we will also support their uptake by interested parties. Similarly, all scientific papers will be published under open-access licenses and will be made available directly after acceptance by the journals. We will use more restrictive licenses, e.g., including clauses to limit commercial use, only in exceptional cases and when it is fully necessary. We will also ensure the reusability of datasets by using the Horizon Europe metadata scheme in the maDMP of the project. For each dataset, the scheme will provide a short description of the data, links with publications and other datasets, and guidelines for the specific dataset related to FAIR practices, allocation of resources, and security and ethical aspects. Lastly, all modelling documentation and results will be formatted using the reporting templates of IPCC AR6 (IAMC format³²) to ensure reusability by the wider modelling community of integrated assessment and climate change mitigation.

³² <https://docs.ece.iiasa.ac.at/iamc.html>

4 Allocation of Resources

Most of the practices described in Chapter 3 for ensuring FAIR data in the project are not requiring any costs from the project. All deliverables and datasets will be uploaded in Zenodo which is free to use, and we will also use the free version of GitHub to store project code. Similarly, the documentation of datasets in the maDMP in ARGOS is also free of charge.

Other activities for ensuring FAIR data (see Chapter 3) require resources which have been considered in the project's Grant Agreement. The extension and hosting of I²AM PARIS requires funds that have been budgeted under WP6, while funds on the development and maintenance of the project website have been considered in the budget of WP7 and the defined purchase costs for ICCS and HOLISTIC. We have also earmarked a part of the budget for publishing in open access journals. Most of this budget is managed by the project coordinator ICCS while all partners have some funds available for individual open access publications related to their work in the project. Suggested options for publishing in open access journals are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Suggested options for open-access scientific publishing in DIAMOND

Access type	Funder	Fees	License
Publish in a fully Open Access journal	Paid through DIAMOND's Grant	Article Processing Charges indicatively ranging between 130€ and 9,500€	CC BY 4.0 CC BY-NC-ND 4.0
Publish in a journal that has the option of Gold Open Access	Paid through publishing agreements between the organisations of project partners and the publisher		

In terms of responsibilities of project partners, ICCS and HOLISTIC will have the overview of all data management in the project. The same partners will ensure that all project data and publications are uploaded in Zenodo and linked to the project website, the maDMP, and the I²AM PARIS platform. The platform will be further developed by HOLISTIC and ICCS, including creating new visualisations and applications based on the project's data. All project partners will be responsible for correct data handling and curation based on the guidelines of the DMP, including that model code is frequently uploaded in the DIAMOND community in GitHub. As also mentioned above, HOLISTIC will be responsible for keeping the website and the platform online and all related project data available for at least three years after the end of the project. For the platform, both ICCS and HOLISTIC are exploring ways to further extend its lifetime.

5 Data Security

We will ensure the security of all project data through robust data storage and secure platforms for communication and data exchange. On the latter, ICCS has created a dedicated workspace in its enterprise version of Microsoft Teams as an internal communication system for video-calls and chatting among project partners (see also Milestone 2). This system is also connected to a secure instance of Microsoft SharePoint which will serve as the exclusive data exchanging system for the project. The management and security of these systems is supported by the admins and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) of ICCS, while their servers are within the EU (Greece), ensuring compliance with GDPR and relevant EU legislation. This will be important as SharePoint will be also used to store contact details of project stakeholders that will need to be fully secure. Similarly, the personal data of newsletter subscribers will be stored in the MailerLite account of HOLISTIC which is also GDPR-compliant.

Apart from the SharePoint, other data storage systems used in the project include the databases of the project website and the I²AM PARIS platform. For both databases, HOLISTIC and ICCS have implemented disaster recovery and backup policies to ensure that the data is safe from loss caused by a disaster such as a critical systems failure, fire, theft, or natural disaster. A similar process is followed by ICCS for the SharePoint system while there is also a versioning system in place that protects the users from accidentally deleting or modifying data.

The project's communities in Zenodo and GitHub will be also used to store data during the process, and, most importantly, to preserve all created datasets and publications after the end of the project. The possibility of data loss in these repositories is very low, as all files and documents are stored in multiple online servers that ensure redundancy. Additionally, it is highly unlikely that these repositories will close operations and, even in that case, they will migrate all content to suitable archives such as the servers of the Software Heritage Foundation and Internet Archive.

6 Ethical Aspects

All data collection and management activities of the project will be compliant with the EU GDPR regulation and with the national privacy and data protection laws of the countries of each partner. For most activities related to model development, there are not ethical or legal aspects apart from respecting the licenses of databases that will be used as sources of modelling inputs. In contrast, ethical aspects become especially important in all the co-creation activities of the project (WP2), where we will collect the perspectives of different project stakeholders through workshops, interviews, and surveys. For the workshops we will use the Chatham House Rule ("when a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule³³, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed."). Minutes of the workshops will heed this rule and will avoid linking individuals to specific statements. The same process will be used for documenting interviews, while surveys will also avoid questions on personal details other than those that are needed for research reasons (e.g., whether a respondent is from academia or policymaking). In all engagement activities, we will ask for an explicit and clear informed consent from the participants. The form used to get this informed consent and further details on ethical aspects of the stakeholder engagement activities of the project will be included within the deliverables of WP2.

As mentioned in Chapter 5, all contact details and feedback of project stakeholders will be stored in the project's secure SharePoint instance while the contact details of the newsletter subscribers will be stored in the MailerLite account of HOLISTIC. Both the SharePoint and the MailerLite instances are hosted within the EU and are GDPR compliant. We will avoid exchanging contact details through unsecure channels such as emails. No personal data transfer will take place from EU to non-EU countries and vice versa. The only information to be collected will be lists of research questions to be extracted by project stakeholders, without capturing who expressed which opinion (anonymisation).

³³ <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>

7 Machine actionable DMP in Argos

In parallel with this report, the DIAMOND maDMP in ARGOS provides a detailed overview of all datasets generated, curated, or managed during the project³⁴. The maDMP will be updated whenever a project dataset is created or modified during the project and a summary of its contents will also be provided in the final update of this report (D6.3). Personnel from ICCS and HOLISTIC will be responsible for creating entries for new datasets in the maDMP while all project partners will be responsible for checking that the metadata provided for their datasets in the maDMP is correct. The following process is being used for creating a new dataset in maDMP:

1. The project partner(s) that created the dataset (henceforth called “data creators”) share it with ICCS and HOLISTIC (“data managers”).
2. The data managers then upload the dataset on Zenodo.
3. The data managers also create a new dataset in the maDMP and prefill it by searching the name of the dataset through the search engine of ARGOS.
4. The data managers complete the metadata for the dataset based on guidance from this report (and its final update, D6.3) as well as link the dataset to relevant deliverables or scientific publications.
5. The data creators are invited to check these metadata and ensure their accuracy.
6. The data managers update the maDMP with the new dataset.

A similar process will be used for new model code (expected to be released in the upcoming months of the project lifetime), where links will be created between the model repositories in GitHub and Zenodo to ensure that the code base of the models receives a unique DOI. This Zenodo entry will be then linked to the maDMP which will be documented with adequate metadata as above. In some cases, such as the OMNIA model, the entire raw input database will be also uploaded in Zenodo. All these processes will be evaluated based on the experience of data managers and creators and may be adapted and optimised further during the project.

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781424>

8 Project publications and datasets as of May 2024

Despite most research outputs of the project expected to be completed in the final two years of the DIAMOND project, multiple publications and datasets have already been released acknowledging DIAMOND. Specifically, eleven articles published in reputable scientific journals have acknowledged the project, while five new datasets have been released to complement some of these studies. In addition, the reports of seven project deliverables have been released in the project website, including our ‘Model development strategy’ and ‘Stakeholder-informed research questions’ that shall guide much of the project onwards.

All publications and datasets are provided as open access on the project website, Zenodo, and—in the case of journal publications—on the websites of their publishers. All journal articles are published strictly as full open access, while the metadata for all datasets have been described in the project’s maDMP in ARGOS, ensuring high accessibility and findability.

Overall, the following scientific articles have been published acknowledging DIAMOND:

1. Moreno, J., Campagnolo, L., Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Gonzalez-Eguino, M., Perdana, S., Van de Ven, D.-J., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Gargiulo, M., Herbst, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Neuner, F., Le Mouël, P., & Vielle, M. (2024). The impacts of decarbonization pathways on Sustainable Development Goals in the European Union. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01309-7>
2. McGookin, C., Süsler, D., Xexakis, G., Trutnevyte, E., McDowall, W., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Few, S., Andersen, P. D., Demski, C., Fortes, P., Simoes, S. G., Bishop, C., Rogan, F., & Ó Gallachóir, B. (2024). Advancing participatory energy systems modelling. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 52, 101319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101319>
3. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2024). Three different directions in which the European Union could replace Russian natural gas. *Energy*, 130254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.130254>
4. Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, D.-J. van de, Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU’s path to net zero. *Joule*, 7(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.11.002>
5. Perdana, S., Vielle, M., & Oliveira, T. D. (2024). The EU carbon border adjustment mechanism: Implications on Brazilian energy intensive industries. *Climate Policy*, 24(2), 260–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2023.2277405>
6. Koutsandreas, D., Trachanas, G. P., Pappis, I., Nikas, A., Doukas, H., & Psarras, J. (2023). A multicriteria modeling approach for evaluating power generation scenarios under uncertainty: The case of green hydrogen in Greece. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 50, 101233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2023.101233>
7. Bailie, A., Pied, M., Vaillancourt, K., Bahn, O., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Wachsmuth, J., Warnke, P., McWilliams, B., Doukas, H., & Nikas, A. (2023). Co-creating Canada’s path to net-zero: A stakeholder-driven modelling analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 4, 100061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100061>
8. Koutsellis, T., Xexakis, G., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Karamaneas, A., Nikas, A., & Doukas, H. (2023). In-

- Cognitive: A web-based Python application for fuzzy cognitive map design, simulation, and uncertainty analysis based on the Monte Carlo method. *SoftwareX*, 23, 101513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2023.101513>
9. Gambhir, A., & Nikas, A. (2023). Seven key principles for assessing emerging low-carbon technological opportunities for climate change mitigation action. *PLOS Climate*, 2(7), e0000235. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000235>
 10. Perdana, S., & Vielle, M. (2023). Carbon border adjustment mechanism in the transition to net-zero emissions: Collective implementation and distributional impacts. *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 25(3), 299–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10018-023-00361-5>
 11. Cassetti, G., Elia, A., Gargiulo, M., & Chiodi, A. (2023). Reinforcing the Paris Agreement: Ambitious scenarios for the decarbonisation of the Central Asian and Caspian region. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 3, 100048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100048>

The following datasets have been released in Zenodo:

1. Moreno, J., Campagnolo, L., Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., González-Eguino, M., Perdana, S., van de Ven, D., Choidi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Gargiulo, M., Herbst, A., Le Mouël, P., & Vielle, M. (2023). Moreno et al_2023_Long-term_SDGsEU_Dataset (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072817>
2. Koutsandreas, D., Trachanas, G. P., Pappis, I., Nikas, A., Doukas, H., & Psarras, J. (2023). Koutsandreas_et_al_2023_ESR_dataset [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10362364>
3. Bailie, A., Pied, M., Vaillancourt, K., Bahn, O., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Wachsmuth, J., Warnke, P., McWilliams, B., Doukas, H., & Nikas, A. (2023). Bailie_et_al_2023_RSET_DATASET [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245443>
4. Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, D.-J. van de, Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). Boitier et al_2023_JOULE_DATASET (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10044337>
5. Gabriele Cassetti, Jon Sampedro, & Dirk-Jan Van de Ven. (2023). DIAMOND D3.1 - Initial development plan: Surveys [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7774836>

The following deliverables have been released in the project website:

1. Briers, S., & Vienni-Baptista, B. (2024). D2.4 Stakeholder-informed research questions (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236722>
2. Koasidis, K., Nikas, A., & Frilingou, N. (2023). D1.1 Quality Management Plan (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236827>
3. Polytanou, G., Xexakis, G., & Koasidis, K. (2023). D7.2 The DIAMOND Project CDE Plan (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236867>
4. Cassola, D., Faberi, S., Sessa, C., Briers, S., & Vienni Baptista, B. (2023). D2.1 Multi Layered Stakeholder Engagement Strategy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237003>

5. Sampedro, J., van de Ven, D.-J., Cassetti, G., Gargiulo, M., Taliotis, C., Vielle, M., Perdana, S., Boitier, B., Giannousakis, A., & Fragkos, P. (2023). D3.1 Model development strategy (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237069>
6. Nikas, A., Xexakis, G., Frilingou, N., & Koasidis, K. (2023). D6.1 Open Data Management Plan (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237118>
7. Polytanou, G., Nikas, A., & Xexakis, G. (2023). D7.1 Visual Identity Website (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237134>

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